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MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS THAT INFLUENCES THE ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS TOWARDS ENTREPRENEURSHIP – WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PALAYAMKOTTAI

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Abstract: This paper presents the motivational factors that influence the students towards entrepreneurship with special reference to Palayamkottai. The main focus of the paper was on to understand student's perception towards entrepreneurship, and the factors that influences the students towards entrepreneurship as their career and to know the conduciveness of education system in creating new entrepreneurs. The data for the study collected 68 respondents from Arts and Science Colleges in Palayamkottai. Various statistical tools are used for the analysis purpose and it is found that the female students are highly influenced by the motivational factors than the male students towards entrepreneurship. The study concludes that, commerce students are more inclined towards entrepreneurship as a career. Today, no matter where you turn, stories abound of the enormous social, economic and educational benefits of entrepreneurship. As a result, entrepreneurship education programs are proliferating in colleges and universities around the country. Whereas 15 years ago only a handful of colleges offered courses in entrepreneurship, today more than thousands of colleges and institutes offer some form of entrepreneurship training in India. This paper is an attempt to study the perception of students of different degree and professional colleges in Moradabad towards entrepreneurship education

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship, Motivational factors, Arts and Science College students*

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship has become an everyday exhortation. Policy makers, economists, academics and even students are talking about it. Today's youth have recognized the various benefits of starting up new business ventures. Today entrepreneurship is considered as one of the best economic development strategies to develop country's economic growth. For most people, the popularity of entrepreneurship is largely due to the positive effects it has on many countries in the form of job and wealth creation. More specifically entrepreneurship is a major engine driving many nation's economic growth, innovation and competitiveness. At the same time, most studies have shown there is a positive relationship between entrepreneurship and economic growth in terms of job creation, firm survival and technological change. Entrepreneurship education programs are proliferating in colleges and universities around the country. Whereas 15 years ago only a handful of colleges offered courses in entrepreneurship, today more than thousands of colleges and institutes offer some

form of entrepreneurship training in India. In developing economy like India, there is always a problem of unemployment. There is always a huge shortage of jobs in the job Market. According to Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy Pvt. Ltd, unemployment rate in India as of Aug 2021 is 8.32 % and it is projected to grow in the subsequent months. To address this issue the government is making a lot of strategic plans and one such initiative is boosting entrepreneurship intent among people. This study explored the factors motivating the Art and Science College students towards entrepreneurship at Tirunelveli District by focusing on entrepreneurial awareness, entrepreneurial characteristics, and the impact of entrepreneurship on the individual and the society.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The students tend to search for business education, which can equip them with necessary entrepreneurial skills and knowledge to run their own business for creating a job from the existing entrepreneurial opportunities. The students move towards the establishment of a new business due to limited capabilities of public and private sectors. Moreover, in India, unemployment has become a national issue as there is increase in the graduates from public and private institutions, who join the labor market. Therefore, the study has evaluated the factors that motivate the young individuals in establishing their own business.

AIM OF THE STUDY

The study has aimed to evaluate the factors that motivate the students towards starting up new business. The study has also drawn some policy implication that has extended positive entrepreneurial attitudes and intentions among the students in Palayamkottai.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The research conducted on the basis of samples, so it would have errors, there may be reluctance on the part of students to fill up the questionnaire. Time and cost are the other two constraints in the study. No distinction was made between undergraduates and post graduates. Moreover this study is restricted to Palayamkottai region only.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the main objectives of the study

1. To analyse the factors that motivates the students towards entrepreneurship on the basis of stream of study.
2. To determine the extent to which how the entrepreneurship education can prepare student to become entrepreneur.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Priya Renjini S (2016) explains in her study that “commerce students are more inclined towards entrepreneurship as a career and concluded that even though students perceive entrepreneurship as a distinguished career, a very few are willing to take up it as their career. The stream wise analysis reveals that commerce students are more inclined towards entrepreneurship as a career. This is due to their awareness about the possibilities in the field. Majority of the respondents agrees that the prevailing education system is conducive to create new entrepreneurs”.

Vivek Raj S N (2018) explain in their study that “The students agreed that entrepreneurship education was beneficial to them in very offsets. Through this type of education an individual can easily make for their survival and have a positive attitude towards what they are learning through this type of education as there are lots of opportunities for them to make them self-sufficient and compete in this phase of world.”

Abdelraheem M. Abualbasal (2019) concluded his study that “The results of this study concluded that the demographic factors affect the students attitude towards entrepreneurship at PSUT in terms of: students’ awareness towards entrepreneurship, students’ perception towards the effect of entrepreneurship on the individual and students’ perception towards the effect of entrepreneurship on the society”.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is the systematic way to solve the research problem. It gives an idea about the various steps systematically adopted by the research with objectives to a study on the factors that motivate the students towards entrepreneurship.

➤ PRIMARY DATA

Primary data are those data that are collected for the first time by the investigation for our use. It will be an original character for our study use questionnaire as primary data. In the study, the primary data was collected from the samples by using questionnaires and personal interviews.

➤ SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data are those data that are already collect and analyzed by someone for some purpose and later for some purpose and the same data used for a different purpose. The data were taken from websites, magazines, and journals.

➤ SAMPLE SIZE

To complete the analysis, a well-structured questionnaire is distributed to 75 and collected back 72 and among them, 5 were incomplete so my sample size is 68.

➤ RESEARCH DESIGN

A research design is considered as the frame or plan for a study that guided as well as helps the data collection and analysis of data. Research design is a detailed blueprint used to guide the research study towards its objectives.

➤ SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Stratified Random sampling method has been taken for this study. Samples are selected at the convenience of the researcher.

➤ STATISTICAL TOOLS

The statistical tools help us to evaluate the problems under the study in a judicial manner. While analyzing the primary data, statistical tools such as percentage analysis, mean, Standard deviation, , and t-test techniques are used in this study.

HYPOTHESES

The following hypothesis made for analysis

1. Opinion regarding statements on motivational factors towards entrepreneurship are equal to average level
2. There is no significant difference between male and female with regard to the factors that motivate the students towards entrepreneurship.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	23	34
	Female	45	66
Age	Below 20	43	63
	20-25	23	33
	Above 25	03	04
Monthly income	Less than 20,000	38	56
	20000 – 40000	16	23
	More than 40000	14	21
Family members doing business	Yes	21	31
	No	47	69
Stream of study	Arts	22	32
	Science	16	24
	Commerce	30	44
Role model in Business	Yes	31	46
	No	37	54

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

- Majority 66% of the students are female.
- Majority 63% of students are below 20 years of age.
- Majority 56% of students have a monthly income of less than 20,000.
- Majority 69% of student's family members are not doing business.
- Majority 44% of the students are from commerce department.
- Majority 54% of students do not have role model in business.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀1: Opinion regarding statements on motivational factors towards entrepreneurship are equal to average level (Average =3)

Motivational Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation	t value	P value
M1: Being the Owner I can take my own decisions	3.32	1.408	1.894	0.234
M2: I can have control over my time	3.41	1.458	2.329	0.226
M3: I may get Public Recognition	3.12	1.191	.814	0.107
M4: I can explore new ideas	3.53	1.355	3.223	0.164
M5: It increases my income	3.46	1.398	2.690	0.194
M6: Lack of Opportunity to continue my higher studies	2.81	1.406	1.121	0.407
M7: Lack of employment opportunity due to this COVID 19	2.81	1.374	1.147	0.396
M8: Family Pressure	2.40	1.362	3.651	0.579

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

Since the P value of all the statements are more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Hence the opinion of the students regard to all the statement of motivational factors is equal to the average level.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between male and female with regard to the factors that motivate the students towards entrepreneurship.

Statements	Male		Female		t value	P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
M1: Being the owner I can take my own decisions	2.91	1.676	3.53	1.217	1.575	.124
M2: I can have control over my time	3.04	1.637	3.60	1.338	1.408	.167
M3: I may get Public Recognition	2.61	1.406	3.38	.984	2.346	.025*
M4: I can explore new ideas	3.09	1.535	3.76	1.209	1.820	.077
M5: It increases my income	2.87	1.604	3.76	1.190	2.340	.025*
M6: Lack of Opportunity to continue my higher studies	2.91	1.443	2.76	1.401	.430	.669
M7: Lack of employment opportunity due to this COVID 19	2.30	1.363	3.07	1.321	2.205	.033*
M8: Family Pressure	2.22	1.413	2.49	1.342	.762	.450

5% level of significance

All *

Since P value is less than 0.05, null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance with regard to the factors that motivate the students towards entrepreneurship. Therefore there is significant difference between male and female with regard to the factors that motivate the students towards entrepreneurship. Based on the mean score, female students have better opinion in motivational factors than the male students.

No star:

Since P value is more than 0.05, null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance with regard to the factors that motivate the students towards entrepreneurship. Therefore there is no significant difference between male and female with regard to that factors that motivate the students towards entrepreneurship.

SUGGESTION

Even though Government has introduced the Student Entrepreneurship Scheme which provides many benefits such as grace marks and attendance to student Entrepreneurs, most of the college students are not aware of it. Open courses and workshops should be organized on entrepreneurship development in colleges. Entrepreneurship development clubs should play a significant role in colleges. These clubs should motivate the students to become entrepreneurs.

CONCLUSION

Even though students perceive entrepreneurship as a notable career, a very few are eager to take up it as their career. The stream wise analysis reveals that commerce students are more prone towards entrepreneurship as a career. This is due to their awareness about the possibilities in the field. Majority of the respondents agrees that the prevailing education system is conducive to create new entrepreneurs. The study concluded that majority female students were interested and optimistic in starting their own business. However, these students lacked knowledge regarding starting new business. The willingness of students to start a new business with established entrepreneurs was observed. The major obstacles faced by students in treading an entrepreneurial path were unwillingness and fear of failure. The study has indicated that enterprise education is required to nurture entrepreneurship among the students at program and course levels. These outcomes would help the policymakers to assess the importance of entrepreneurship education because India needs to create a lot of employment opportunities for its growing youth population, where start-ups can help in this respect.

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